

To Study The Variation of Dark Energy Scalar Fields In The Homogeneous Universe Using k-Essence Scalar Field Model

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ABSTRACT

A lagrangian is set up using inhomogeneous k-essence scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ where the kinetic term is dominated over the potential term. The k-essence field is taken to be the source of dark energy in the universe. The lagrangian is solved considering inhomogeneous LTB metric and the expressions for $\phi_1(r)$, $\phi_2(t)$ is obtained. It is shown that under certain approximation, the LTB metric reduces to flat FLRW metric for a homogeneous universe. The FLRW metric is written in the terms of dark energy fields $\phi(r, t)$. Then, $\phi_2(t)$ is written in the terms of scale factor $a(t)$. The evolution of $\phi(r, t)$, $\phi_2(t)$ and $\phi_1(r)$ is studied using several plots. The evolution of dark energy fields also determine the form of FLRW metric, which in turn determines the geometry of the universe itself. From the plots it is determined that the epoch where the homogeneous and inhomogeneous field $\phi_2(t)$, $\phi_1(r)$ intersects each other. The study shows how the geometry of the universe is changing with the change of dark energy scalar fields.

Keywords:

Early Universe, k-Essence Scalar Field, Scale factor, Dark energy, Expanding universe, Inhomogeneous cosmology

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Notations and Abbreviations

- $\phi(r, t)$ = Spherically symmetric k-essence scalar field
- $a(t)$ = Scale factor of the expanding universe
- $\phi_1(r)$ = Inhomogeneous part of the k-essence field
- $\phi_2(t)$ = Homogeneous part of the k-essence field
- $\dot{\phi}_2(t)$ = Rate of change of homogeneous part of the k-essence field
- FLRW Metric = Friedmann–Lemaître–Robertson–Walker Metric for homogeneous universe
- LTB Metric = Lemaitre-Bondi-Tolman Metric for inhomogeneous universe
- SNe Ia = Supernova type Ia

Introduction

The universe today we observe is going through a late time accelerated expansion. The observation of the luminosity distance from the SNe Ia data clearly indicates this late time expansion. The observations from Planck Satellite, Baryon Acoustic Oscillations (BAO), power spectrum of the matter distribution of the universe also suggests the same. In an expanding universe the scale factor is always changing, that is it is a function of time. A scale factor for our universe could be defined as the rate at which the space itself is increasing for an outside observer, in other words it is just the ratio between actual physical distance and co-moving distance. The scale factor $a(t)$ of the universe is a very important parameter to understand the evolution of the universe. So the theoretical basis of understanding the evolution of the universe and how the expansion came into place is mainly confined in relating several theoretical models with the scale factor of the universe. Different studies suggest the Dark Energy to be the key candidate which is responsible for this late time accelerated expansion. Dark energy is a mysterious form of energy which imparts negative pressure which counters the gravitational attraction resulting in accelerated phase. Recent studies from Planck Probe shows that 68.3% of the total contents of the present universe is dark energy. The form of Dark energy is still under study.

The approach to explain dark energy theoretically contains several diverse theo-

ries. One of those is $\Lambda - CDM$ model. This model can efficiently explain various cosmological observations but at the same time it has a major problem with the standard model of particle physics which called fine-tuning problem. Another tries to explain the Dark Energy contains two approaches: a) One of those is to modify the stress-energy tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$ of the Einsteins's equation that exerts negative pressure. These are called Modified matter model. b) Another approach includes the modification of geometric part of the Einstein's equation, which is called Modified Gravity models. This includes models like $f(R)$ gravity, Scalar-tensor model, Brane World model etc. One of the modified matter models is Quintessence model. It has a potential term dominated lagrangian i.e. the potential energy of the field drives the late time accelerated expansion. On the other hand models like Tachyon model has a kinetic term dominated lagrangian and that kinetic term gives rise to late time acceleration. These are called k-essence model. These type of models with non-canonical kinetic terms in the action are strong candidates of dark energy. This type of theory with non-canonical kinetic terms were first proposed by Born and Infeld to get rid of the infinite self energy of the electron. In our context the k-essence lagrangian is taken as $L = -V(\phi)F(X)$ where $X = \partial^\mu\phi\partial_\mu\phi$. Here we have assumed that $F(X)$ is more general function of kinetic energy with some complicated functional relationship.

Earlier study suggests that a lagrangian can be set up for the early universe, when the universe is flat and homogeneous, with two generalised coordinates $q = \ln a(t)$ and the k-essence scalar field $\phi(t)$ with some complicated polynomial relation between them. Here it is assumed that the potential $V(\phi)$ is constant. The study considered the scale factor to be much smaller than today's universe but much larger than the inflationary phase. Under certain assumptions the lagrangian takes the form of a harmonic oscillator with time varying frequency. In this framework a general scaling relation is obtained viz. $XF_X^2 = Ca(t)^{-6}$. The solution of the la-

grangian gives a growing solution of the scale factor which indicates the expanding universe. The cosmological temperature T is inversely proportional to the scale factor. Using this the calculation of the quantum fluctuations of q gives the probability amplitude of fluctuations in the temperature present in the background radiation of the universe. This study also accounts for the chaotic inflation though this model did not take account the inflationary period.

In an another study, the lagrangian is set up using the homogeneous scalar field $\phi(t)$ in FLRW universe that is in a flat homogeneous universe. From the observed data of SNe Ia and Hubble telescope, the scale factors of several epochs have been calculated. Then it is plugged into the quantum amplitudes calculated from the fluctuations in $q(a(t))$. It gives certain results as a) The observed variation of rate of change of scale factor b) The observed epoch when the universe went from a decelerating phase to accelerated phase of expansion. The results from the Planck Probe shows the inhomogeneities present in the CMBR is non-gaussian. To account that inhomogeneity, the scalar field is made homogeneous by introducing a small perturbation in it, viz. $\phi(t, x) = \phi(t)(1 + f)$, where f is a small inhomogeneity parameter. It is shown that the presence of inhomogeneity can affect the value of the epoch when this transition has occurred. The value of inhomogeneity parameter must be a bit negative to match the observations.

A recent study has done where the inhomogeneity is taken into account more profoundly where the scalar field itself taken to be inhomogeneous $\phi(r, t)$. The inhomogeneous metric is nothing but the perturbations from FLRW metric. One such kind of spherically symmetric, inhomogeneous metric is LTB metric. If the scalar field can be assumed to be decomposed as $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$, it leads to a scaling relation for the inhomogeneous scalar fields, $X F_X^2 = C T^{-4}$. Under certain assumptions the LTB metric could be reduced to FLRW metric, and the scaling relation is then become the scaling relation obtained for a homogeneous

scalar field. In this scenario the FLRW metric could be written in terms of the dark energy field ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 . It clearly indicates that the k-essence field or the dark energy field has a key role to determining the value of the metric which in turns determines the geometry of the universe itself. It is one of the most important result that can be drawn from the models of this kind.

In this study I have obtained a relation between homogeneous part of the dark energy field $\phi_2(t)$ and scale factor $a(t)$. Using the values of $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ both are plotted against each other. It shows the both homogeneous and inhomogeneous part of the dark energy scalar field evolves with different epochs. Then the overall field that is $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$ is plotted against scale factor $a(t)$ to show the overall variation of the k-essence field with time. The epoch when $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ intersects each other is extracted from the graphs. This overall evolution in the fields determine How the FLRW metric evolves with time. Thus the evolution of the dark energy fields has a very deep connection with evolution of the geometry of the universe itself.

Methodology

2.0.1 Background

The scaling relation obtained from the LTB metric for inhomogeneous cosmology can be reduced to the homogeneous cosmology under certain identifications of the metric parameters. Below we will see that the scaling relation that is obtained from the LTB metric is reduced to the one we will obtain from the FLRW metric where the metric parameter is completely written in terms of the dark-energy scalar field. For an Inhomogeneous universe one can use the metric as Lemaitre-Bondi-Tolman metric given by

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + Y'^2 + Y^2[d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2]$$

Constructing the k-essence lagrangian and using the LTB metric a scaling relation could be introduced as $XF_X^2 = CT^{-4}$, where, it is taken that $Y(r, t) = f^{2/3}(r, t)$ and $f(r, t) = R(r)T(t)$.

The k-essence field is taken as $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$. Now solving the Euler-Lagrange Equations following relations are found:-

$$\phi_1(r) = \sqrt{2Br} \tag{2.1}$$

$$\phi_2(t) = -\frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha}(1 + 4\alpha t) \quad (2.2)$$

$$T(t) = \frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \quad (2.3)$$

Here, B , D and α are constants and $\alpha \ll 1$

Under the limit of $Y(t, r) \rightarrow a(t)r$ the LTB metric reduces to FLRW metric i.e. inhomogeneous universe reduces to homogeneous universe.

Using this limit and FLRW metric, it can be shown that

$$a(t) = T^{\frac{2}{3}} = \left[\frac{\dot{\phi}_2^2 D^2}{2\dot{\phi}_2^2 - 4B} \right]^{\frac{1}{6}} \quad (2.4)$$

The scaling relation is also reduced to $XF_X^2 = Ca^{-6}(t)$.

The FLRW metric can be written as-

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - \left[\frac{\dot{\phi}_2^2 D^2}{2\dot{\phi}_2^2 - 4B} \right]^{\frac{1}{6}} 2B[d\phi_1^2 + \phi_1^2 d\theta^2 + \phi_1^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2] \quad (2.5)$$

Here, we see that the inhomogeneous LTB metric is reduced to the homogeneous FLRW metric under certain limit and can be written completely with the dark energy scalar field which changed the space time geometry. The scaling relation is the same as the scaling relation obtained in the inhomogeneous cosmology.

2.0.2 Theoretical Method

Now, it is clear from the equation eq. [2.4] and [2.3]

$$a(t) = T^{\frac{2}{3}}(t) = \left[\frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \right]^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (2.6)$$

So, the value of t in terms of $a(t)$

$$t = \frac{D^2}{2\alpha^2 a^6(t)} \quad (2.7)$$

Putting the value of t in eq.[2.2] we get,

$$\boxed{\phi_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha} \left[1 + \frac{4D^2}{2\alpha a^6(t)} \right]} \quad (2.8)$$

Using eq. [2.8] and eq. [2.1] I have plotted ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 with $a(t)$ and r .

Now I have assumed that the k-essence field,

$$\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t) \quad (2.9)$$

Using eq. [2.8] and eq. [2.1]

$$\boxed{\phi(r, t) = \sqrt{2B}r - \frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha} \left[1 + \frac{4D^2}{2\alpha a^6(t)} \right]} \quad (2.10)$$

Using this I have plotted the variation of $\phi(r, t)$ with $a(t)$ and r .

Results

3.0.1 Plotting $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$

Here we have shown the plots using different combinations for values of B and D *viz.* a) both equal b) both unequal c) B is negative and D is positive d) both fractional e) one is fraction and another is integer. Different plots are shown in the following sections. We set the value $\alpha = 0.1$.

Figure 3.1: Here, $B=0.1$, $D=0.1$. Here ϕ_2 intersects ϕ_1 at approx. $a(t) \approx 0.07$

Figure 3.2: Here, $B=3$, $D=2$. ϕ_2 intersects ϕ_1 at $a(t) \approx 0.12$

Figure 3.3: Here, $B=-3$, $D=0.2$. ϕ_2 intersects ϕ_1 at $a(t) \approx 0.10$

Figure 3.4: Here, $B=-0.7$, $D=0.2$. ϕ_2 intersects with ϕ_1 at $a(t) \approx 0.11$

Figure 3.5: Here, $B=-4$, $D=-5$. ϕ_2 intersects with ϕ_1 at $a(t) \approx 0.20$

3.0.2 The variation of $\phi(r, t)$

Here, the plots are shown for the variation of dark energy field $\phi(r, t)$ with the scale factor $a(t)$. The combinations of B and D used here is same as the above.

Figure 3.6: $B=0.4, D=3$

Figure 3.7: $B=3, D=0.5$

Figure 3.8: Here, $B=D=2$

Figure 3.9: $B=-0.8, D=0.3$

Figure 3.10: $B=-0.5, D=2$

Figure 3.11: $B=-5, D=3$

Discussions

Now, from the calculations and plots from the above, I will discuss the various outcomes of this study.

- In the section 2.0.2, equation (2.8) suggests that the homogeneous part of the dark energy scalar field ϕ_2 becomes inversely proportional with 6th power of scale factor $a(t)$. It could be shown from that equation that as scale factor becomes larger, the second term in the third bracket of equation (2.8) becomes smaller and smaller. Then it could be neglected and the homogeneous dark energy field becomes constant *i.e.* $\phi_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha}$.
- In section 3.0.1, the plots between ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 clearly shows there is an overlapping of ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 at a particular epoch. The value of that epoch depends on the magnitude of the constants B and D . It is evident from the graphs that more the value of B , larger the value of the scale factor $a(t)$ at which they are intersecting each other. The value of ϕ_2 becomes constant with the scale factor just after the intersecting point.
- As it is seen that for larger values of scale factor $a(t)$, the homogeneous dark energy field ϕ_2 becomes constant. Then, the equation (2.10) shows

that the total dark energy scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ becomes the function of r only. Thus for larger values of scale factor the dark energy scalar field becomes inhomogenous.

- The variation of $\phi(r, t)$ from the section 3.0.2 shows the inhomogeneous nature of the scalar field $\phi(r, t)$. The field at first increases with $a(t)$, then after a point becomes constant with increase of scale factor. The graph becomes steeper when the value of D is smaller. If the value of B is large then the overall variation with r slightly decreases, as seen from the Fig. 3.11 .
- The plots in the section 3.0.2 also shows that at the very beginning, there is zero value of the dark energy scalar field $\phi(r, t)$. After some epochs, the scalar field starts to increase. This type variation indicates the origin of dark energy field happens after some time from the zeroth epoch, i.e. at the point where $a(t) = 0$. This kind of behaviour needs further study to shed light on this.

Conclusion

In the study, a lagrangian is set up for inhomogeneous k-essence scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ and a spherically symmetric inhomogeneous LTB metric is used here. The lagrangian is solved under the assumption that $\phi(r, t) = \phi_1(r) + \phi_2(t)$. The solution of the lagrangian gives the values of $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ for inhomogeneous universe. Then it is shown that under some certain assumptions the LTB metric is reduced to flat FLRW metric for homogeneous universe. The FLRW metric is written completely in terms of dark energy scalar field $\phi_1(r)$ and $\phi_2(t)$. Then using the relations as expression of t in terms of $a(t)$ is derived. From this expression a relation between $\phi_2(t)$ and $a(t)$ is established to understand how the dark energy field evolve at different epochs. Then, $\phi_2(t)$, $\phi_1(r)$ is plotted against $a(t)$. The total k-essence scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ is also plotted against scale factor $a(t)$. Here, I have used various values of constants B and D viz. a) both equal b) both unequal c) B is negative and D is positive d) both fractional e) one is fraction and another is integer. The data from the plots are then extracted and it gives the value of scale factor $a(t)$ at which $\phi_2(t)$ intersects with $\phi_1(r)$.

The study has found that under some certain assumptions, the terms in FLRW metric can be written completely in terms of dark energy scalar field $\phi(r, t)$. This suggests that the geometry of the space-time is determined by the value of the dark energy field components. The study shows that for larger values of scale

factor, the homogeneous part of the dark energy scalar field ϕ_2 becomes constant (independent of $a(t)$). At some particular epoch both the inhomogeneous and homogeneous dark energy scalar field ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 intersects with each other. The value of the scale factor at the point of intersection depend on the constants B and D ; That value increases with increase of B . At larger values of scale factor, the total dark energy scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ becomes inhomogeneous *i.e.* the function of r only. The plots in section 3.0.2 affirm this fact. From the plots of $\phi(r, t)$ it is shown that the increase of $\phi(r, t)$ becomes more rapid when D is smaller. The larger value of B decreases the overall variation of $\phi(r, t)$ with r . The plots from this section also infers that the dark energy scalar field $\phi(r, t)$ is zero at the points close to $a(t) = 0$. After a certain epoch it starts to increase rapidly. This observation is significant to understand the origin of dark energy at the earliest phase of the universe, although it requires further study.

This work is an extrapolation of previous works of k-essence scalar field models. It suggests that a single scalar field is sufficient to take account for dark energy, as well as to explain the late time accelerated expansion of the universe. My study illuminated on the evolution of the dark energy field with the evolution of the universe. It shows how the two components of single dark energy scalar field behaves with the increases of scale factor and also the overall behaviour of that scalar field is portrayed here. The values of scale factor extracted from the recent JWST observations will definitely fine tune this work more efficiently. However, the nature of the graphs could be different if the inhomogeneous LTB metric is considered throughout the study. Currently, it is under study. This study suggests that the values of B and D is very much important to calculate the accurate values for the dark energy field as well as plotting the exact nature of the graph. The value of B and D can be obtained from the observational data, which will further improve this work.

Appendices

Calculation of $\phi_2(t)$ in terms of $a(t)$

The relation between the $a(t)$ and $T(t)$ is given by the equation (2.4)

$$a(t) = T^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Now from equation (2.4)

$$T(t) = \frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Thus, it can be easily shown that,

$$a(t) = \left[\frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \right]^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

So, from the above,

$$a^{\frac{3}{2}} = \frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}t^{1/4}} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\Rightarrow t^{1/4} = \frac{D^{1/2}}{2\alpha^{1/4}a^{3/2}} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Thus the equation of ϕ_2 in terms of $a(t)$ will be,

$$\boxed{\phi_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2B}}{8\alpha} \left[1 + \frac{4D^2}{2\alpha a^6(t)} \right]} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

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